

DARIAH Virtual Annual Event 2020: Scholarly Primitives

Unus pro omnibus!
Generic research tool for all Humanities disciplines.

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In the next 10 Minutes...

Our Backstory

Data in the Humanities: a heterogeneous blend

DaSCH Service Platform

Next steps

Our Backstory

Data and Service Center for the Humanities → dasch.swiss

- ▶ Operating a platform for humanities research data
- ▶ Ensuring access to this data
- ▶ Networking of data with other databases is to be promoted (linked open data)
- ▶ Creating added value for research and the interested public

Our Backstory

The digital equivalent of Warburg's Mnemosyne

Our Backstory

The digital equivalent of Warburg's Mnemosyne

Data in the Humanities: a heterogeneous blend

Projects from history, art history, media, music and film studies, etc.

- ▶ Incunabula Basiliensis: Books
- ▶ Photo collections: Photographs
- ▶ Bernoulli Euler: Books, notes and mathematical formulas
- ▶ Lexicon Iconographicum Mythologiae Classicae (LIMC): Encyclopedia
- ▶ Archive of the Swiss Society of Folklore: Photographs, moving images, magazines
- ▶ PhD projects from all disciplines in the Humanities

Data in the Humanities: a heterogeneous blend

Do various projects need different databases? RDF as a flexible solution

Resource → Property → Value

Data is represented as “triplet”

Data in the Humanities: a heterogeneous blend

Do various projects need different databases? RDF as a flexible solution

Connect properties and extend the data

Data in the Humanities: a heterogeneous blend

Do various projects need different databases? RDF as a flexible solution

Each project can have it's own ontologies

DaSCH Service Platform

Backend: API with RDF triplestore and IIIF media server

DaSCH Service Platform

Frontend: Different apps can be built and use the same data

DaSCH Service Platform

Generic web application

DaSCH Service Platform: Generic web application

Easy-to-use ontology editor

Define the metadata for resource class

Photograph

⋮	Property label *	Property type *		🗑️
1)	Title	Text: Short	▼	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Multiple values?	<input type="checkbox"/> Required field?		Reset
⋮	Property label *	Property type *	Select reresource class	🗑️
2)	Photographer	Link: Other resource ...	Person	▼
	<input type="checkbox"/> Multiple values?	<input type="checkbox"/> Required field?		Reset
⋮	Property label *	Property type *		🗑️
3)	Comment	Text: Paragraph	▼	
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Multiple values?	<input type="checkbox"/> Required field?		Reset +

Back **Submit**

DaSCH Service Platform: Generic web application

Three different ways to search data

The image shows a search interface for the DaSCH Service Platform. At the top, there is a search bar with a dropdown menu for 'Filter by project' set to 'All Projects' and a search input field. Below the search bar are two tabs: 'advanced' and 'expert'. Two arrows point from these tabs to two separate search modal windows.

Advanced search

Select an Ontology
The incunabula ontol... ▾

Select a Resource Class (option...
Book ▾

Select Properties Comparison Operator text value
Creator ▾ matches ▾ Brant

+ -

Reset Search

Expert search

Write your Gvsearch query

```
PREFIX knora-api: <http://api.knora.org/ontology/knora-api/v2#>
PREFIX incunabula: <https://api.dasch.swiss/ontology/0803/incunabula/v2#>

CONSTRUCT {
  ?book knora-api:isMainResource true .
  ?book incunabula:title ?title .
} WHERE {
  ?book a incunabula:book .
  ?book incunabula:title ?title .
}
```

Reset Search

DaSCH Service Platform: Generic web application

Search results and resource viewer

The screenshot displays the DaSCH Service Platform interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text "All Projects" and "Search". Below the search bar, there are tabs for "List" and "Grid", and a page indicator "1 - 14 of 14".

The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column shows a list of search results. The first result is for page "1r", described as the beginning of a text with a large initial "T". The second result is for page "o1v", described as the reverse side of a title page with a woodcut illustration of a monk. The third result, which is highlighted, is for page "q1v", described as the beginning of a chapter with a woodcut illustration of a young man in a landscape.

The right column shows the detailed view of the selected resource, "q1v". It includes a "Page identifier" field with the value "q1v", a "Description" field with the text "Beginn Kapitel 107. Holzschnitt zu Kap. 107: Vom Lohn der Weisheit Ein junger Mann in weitem pelzgefütterten Mantel steht in einer Landschaft vor einem Gelehrten, der ein offenes Buch vor sich hält. Am Himmel erscheinen eine Krone und eine Narrenkappe. Die Krone steckt in einem senkrechten, die Kappe in einem schräg gestellten Stab, 11,5 x 8,3 cm.", and a "Sequence number" field with the value "245". Other fields include "Citation/reference", "Comment", "Original filename", "Randleistentyp links", "Randleistentyp rechts", "Transkription", "has image file", "has Standoff Link to", and "has incoming link".

DaSCH Service Platform: Generic web application

Mark regions on images and in text, transcribe moving images and audio files

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled "Source XYZ - S-U-ID" with the URL "http://suid.app.dosch.swiss/source/[n]". The page header is "Source XYZ: Transcription" and includes a search bar and a "Filter by project" dropdown. The main content area is split into two panels. The left panel displays a video player with a black and white image of a steam locomotive. Below the video player, there is a section titled "Night Mail" with a "Sequence" field containing "00:02:55 - 00:04:33" and a "Title" field. A vertical list of horizontal bars represents marked regions, with a legend on the right for "Transcript", "Description", "Camera", and "Sound". A yellow "SAVE" button is located at the bottom right of this section. The right panel contains a table with the following columns: Seq, Start, End, Title, Transcript, Description, Camera, and Sound. The table has four rows of data:

Seq	Start	End	Title	Transcript	Description	Camera	Sound
01	00:00:00	00:00:42	Intro				
02	00:00:42	00:01:28	Title				
03	00:01:28	00:02:02					
04	00:02:02	00:02:55					

DaSCH Service Platform: Generic web application

Data exchange: Export results as CSV, XML, JSON and share resources, search results or search filters with project collaborators

Search & Find — SU-1-D

http://euid.app.dasch.ethz.ch/search

Found 174 results

Filter by project Search

List Grid Table Sort Export

First property as Title
just a few properties here as a preview click on the element to open it
Last changes on dd. mm. yyyy hh:mm by user View the history

First property as Title
just a few properties here as a preview click on the element to open it
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First property as Title
just a few properties here as a preview click on the element to open it
Last changes on dd. mm. yyyy hh:mm by user View the history

3
Sources Selected

✕ Clear Selection

DaSCH Service Platform: Generic web application

Select multiple resources and compare them

The screenshot displays a web browser window titled "Compare view - S-U-I-D" with the URL http://suid.app.dasch.swiss/compare/sources/ri_1/ri_2/ri_3/ri_4/ri_5. The interface features a "Compare" header with a search bar and a user profile icon. Below the header, four source panels are visible, each labeled "Source XYZ":

- Top-left panel:** A DVD cover for "Night Mail" from the "BBC West Highland" series. The cover features a red steam locomotive and the text "THE RSCG CLASSIC COLLECTION".
- Top-right panel:** A video player showing a black and white scene of a steam locomotive on a railway track. The video is titled "Night Mail (Making of...) Scene 5".
- Bottom-left panel:** A poster for "Night Mail" featuring a stylized black silhouette of a locomotive against a blue sky with a full moon. The text "NIGHT MAIL" is prominently displayed.
- Bottom-right panel:** Another poster for "Night Mail", similar to the one in the bottom-left panel, but with a different layout and text.

Each panel includes a small thumbnail icon, a title, and a description. The bottom-right panel also shows several lines of placeholder text.

Next steps

- ▶ More than 40 projects are queuing to get access to DaSCH Service Platform
- ▶ Implementing missing features
- ▶ Going live in February 2021

Questions? Contact us!

The code of our tools is open source and available on GitHub:
github.com/dasch-swiss

Get more information about us on:
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